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Multi-modal sorting in plastic and wood waste streams

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ABSTRACT

Addressing the escalating waste crisis necessitates innovative waste management strategies, particularly valorisation techniques, the efficiency of which is dictated by the purity of the feedstock. In order to mitigate the segregation challenges encountered in complex and non-homogeneous waste streams, this work proposes a vision-based architecture ample for effective sorting of parts based on shape and material-related properties. The proposed work encapsulates a novel deep learning multi-modal approach, in which multiple parallel auto-encoders are used to extract spatio-spectral information from the RGB and multi-spectral sensors and project them in a common latent space. By decoding the latent space representations, the class of each object is picked out, thus guiding the robotic sub-system accordingly. To support the proposed deep architecture, a dataset, called Multispectral Mixed Waste Dataset (MMWD) was produced, containing multi-spectral data from the visible (16 bands), near-infrared (25 bands) regions of the electromagnetic spectrum and RGB (3 bands) data. The dataset includes the following seven plastic and wood wastes: Polypropylene (PP), Polyethylene Terephthalate (PET), Low-Density Polyethylene (LDPE), High-Density Polyethylene (HDPE), Medium Density Fibreboard (MDF), Melamine Faced Chipboards (MFC), and Oak Veneer samples. For the localisation of waste along the conveyor belt, YOLO v8 is used to achieve 99.5% mean average precision (mAP50). In the classification task, where the multi-modal approach was followed, the overall accuracy achieved is 96% with the prediction recall being greater than 95% for the majority of classes under examination.

1. Introduction

According to OECD report OECD (2022), plastic waste generation has doubled in the last two decades, with an estimated 3.4 billion tonnes of waste to be produced by 2050 Kaza et al. (2018). The vast majority of it ends up in landfills, being burned or seeping into the environment, and only 9% is properly recycled OECD (2022). The environmental impacts are becoming increasingly concerning, leading waste authorities and the scientific community to invest in the development of smart and

innovative ways to manage waste and reduce landfilling. Contemporary research has focused on developing valorisation techniques, as part of tertiary recycling, to degrade polymers and prepare feedstock for fuel or refineries Roy et al. (2021). Nonetheless, barriers such as the existence of complicated fractions in waste streams (i.e. pollutants, multi-layer materials, a mixture of plastics, woods and other garbage) that cannot be processed efficiently contribute to the low rate of material recycling Singh and Ordoñez (2016) Specifically mixed solid waste streams, that contain plastics and wood by-products, often occur from discarded

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Fig. 1. The illustration depicts the CPSS, which consists of a conveyor, a mechanical separator, a two-stage multi-camera identification system, two robotic arms, containers, and a central processing unit Konstantinidis et al. (2023b).

furniture where plastic parts (i.e. handles, knobs, etc.) are installed on wooden frames. Another common source of mixed plastic-wood waste streams are construction and demolition sites, where plastic equipment and wooden parts are involved, as well as packing waste that consist of wooden crates or pallets wrapped with plastic material. Menegaki and Damigos (2018)

The unsorted plastics, in the aforementioned streams, may gradually fragment into microplastics, infiltrating ecosystems and water bodies, while unmanaged wood waste contributes to deforestation and habitat degradation. Additionally, the inconsistency in material quality arising from unmethodical sorting can hinder recycling efforts, affecting the viability of recycled products Asamoah et al. (2020); Yusuf et al. (2022). Therefore, there is an urgent need for a new solution to accurately identify the type of plastic and the type of wood within wastes, increasing the amount of such products being valorised.

In the traditional recycling process, a small number of wastes are manually sorted and reused or valorised in particular industrial processes, while the great majority are disposed due to the lack of sorting technology and circularity methods Konstantinidis et al. (2022). These restrictions reduce the number of recyclable materials, increasing the worldwide waste footprint Wilts et al. (2021a). This difficulty can be handled by following Industry 4.0 and the Circular Economy principles, with the aim to develop intelligent sorting systems, capable of categorizing materials effectively, without human intervention; thus leading to new valorisation ways Konstantinidis et al. (2023b). As a physical intermediate layer between consumers and valorisation processes, using advanced robotics and multi-sensor systems, the Cyber-physical Sorting System (CPSS), presented in Fig. 1, is able to identify the type of unsorted materials and classify them.

By using automated sorters, the quality of waste stream aggregation is increased.

In plastic valorisation chains (Fig. 2), the proposed CPSS could be used to separate PLA (Polylactic Acid) for the PET-based product instead of the expensive thermal depolymerization of PLA, which requires a catalyst and a multi-step purification process Piemonte et al. (2013). In the case of glycolysis and hydrolysis methods, where the PET wastes are up-scaled, the clean feedstock can be provided by aggregating PET without dyes or additives Akovali et al. (2013). Additives (viz. HDPE and LDPE), in the feedstock play a crucial role in the thermal or catalytic pyrolysis of PolyEthylene (PE) and PolyStyrene (PS) Bora et al. (2020); Mo et al. (2013), while the existence of plastics in the catalytic dechlorination method of PolyVinyl Chloride (PVC) waste affects significantly in the recycled product Kosloski-Oh et al. (2021). In recent years, a wide range of automated sorting systems has emerged, to tackle the versatile challenges of waste management. Wilts et al. proposed a segregation system consisting of two robotic arms and a conveyor

belt. The mechanical system was controlled by machine learning (ML) models, trained to identify and sort 13 types of waste (ferrous metals, non-ferrous metals, textiles, cardboard, HDPE, LDPE, PP, wood, PET, paper, other mixed plastics, Tetra Pak, printing and green waste). The proposed system, despite its high recognition performance and the purity of the sorted materials, was not able to achieve high recovery rates Wilts et al. (2021b). Another study introduces a new modelling tool for Mixed Solid Waste (MSW) sorting that considers operational conditions, process sequence, waste composition, and physical properties. It utilizes a mixed modelling approach combining mechanistic modelling and transfer coefficients, validated through a real case study. The tool highlights the effects of process sequence and operating conditions on unit operation sorting efficiency, demonstrating its advantages over traditional transfer coefficient methods Tanguay-Rioux et al. (2022). Nonetheless, the intelligence behind these smart systems resides in the machine or deep learning classifiers. These classifiers are capable of accurately categorizing various types of waste, and their current state are documented in the Related work (Section 2).

To support the aforementioned segregation solutions, a deep learning multi-modal framework called *multi-modal classifier*, has been designed, developed, and validated for plastic waste streams and wood by-products separation by leveraging advances in the sensor industry and cutting-edge deep learning architecture. The module is also capable of providing pick coordinates to the robotic arm, taking into account the speed of the conveyor. Utilizing hyper-spectral imaging modalities in conjunction with visual modalities has enabled the realisation of dependable and accurate segmentation and categorization features within moving and complex industrial environments. The spatial spectral information captured by a hyperspectral camera can range from 470 nm up to 975 nm. Those extended frequency bands offer valuable information that can not be captured by traditional imaging systems. On the contrary, common RGB cameras are used to localise waste and increase the level of intelligence. The manipulation of hyper-spectral and visual information shapes a rich and challenging research topic. The contributions of our work are summarized as follows:

- The introduction of a vision-based module capable of preparing clear feed-stocks for better and more efficient valorisation techniques in autonomous sorters.
- The design and implementation of an accurate deep learning multi-modal approach, utilizing auto-encoders for the purpose of plastic and wood by-product wastes classification.
- The analysis of how different modalities (viz. RGB, VIS and NIR images) affect the performance in plastic-wood products separation and the exploration of the capabilities of more fine characterization in both plastic waste (PET, PP, HDPE, LDPE) and wood by-products (MDF, MFC, Oak Veneer).
- The generation of a dataset, dubbed MMWD, containing RGB and multi-spectra instances of plastic waste and wood by-products, with the aim to avail the research community in assessing other multi-modal architectures.

To this end, Section 2 describes the related work, while Section 3 provides a high-level description of the system architecture and the modules implemented for the needs of this work is provided. The outputs of each module, along with their flow through the pipeline, are also discussed. Section 4 presents the dataset generation methodology and a more deep technical view of our implementation of the aforementioned modules. In addition, the technical details about the deep-learning models as well as the experimental results and the performance of the proposed system are discussed in Section 5. Finally, in Section 6 a discussion about the main conclusions of this study and the future steps are provided.

Fig. 2. The image illustrates the placement of the CPSS within the plastic valorization chains.

2. Related work

In this section, we discuss the development of vision-based waste sorting techniques, with an emphasis on plastic and wood waste separation. In recent years, there has been an increase in the number of research articles addressing waste management and segregation, with a focus on sensor technology and basic processing techniques rather than on advanced deep learning techniques.

An affordable, yet efficient, way to discriminate different types of plastic waste is with the use of optical sensors, i.e. RGB cameras. Altikat et al. (2022), implemented a 5-layer Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) to classify waste samples as Paper, Glass, Plastic and Organic. The proposed architecture was able to predict a sample's class with **89.17%** total accuracy in the train set and **70%** in the test set. In another study, a transfer learning scheme was proposed in an attempt to reduce training times, utilize deeper network architecture and take advantage of prior low-level knowledge, in order to discriminate various types of waste. In detail, the model classified samples from the NWNUTRASH dataset as Paper, Plastic, Glass, Metal and Fabric with **82.8%** overall accuracy Zhang et al. (2021). Although identifying plastics within a mixture of urban waste is an important step in waste segregation, in order to further boost the plastics recycling process a plastic-oriented system is needed that is capable of classifying plastic waste to their respective subcategories. In this manner, Bobulski and Kubanek (2021) proposed a deep-learning architecture to identify four of the most common household plastic waste types - HDPE, PET, PP, PS. The proposed model consists of 15 convolutional layers that extract spatial information from RGB images in order to feed a block of fully connected neurons that classified the samples to their respective classes. The model achieved **99%** accuracy during the training phase, which however during the testing phase dropped dramatically to **74%**.

A different category of optical sensors that show the potential in providing highly informative data for the classification of plastic waste is the Near Infrared (NIR) Hyperspectral cameras. Those sensors, capture images with good spatial resolution while integrating dense information about the spectral properties of the object under examination. A Specim FX17 NIR hyperspectral camera, capable of capturing 224 frequency bands in the range of 900-1700 nm, has been used in order to train a gradient boosting tree-like algorithm to identify 8 types of plastic waste Sbrana et al. (2023). Black plastics have been included in the experiments, which resulted in a relatively low overall accuracy, equal to **79%**. However, when only the coloured and transparent plastics were taken under consideration the model's accuracy raised to **90%**. In another study, a more conventional approach was adopted, achieving however remarkable results. In detail, Bonifazi et al. (2018) proposed a pipeline for the characterization of HDPE, LDPE, PP, PS and PVC. The pipeline comprising spectra normalization and Savitzky-Golay first-order gradient calculation as preprocessing steps, in order for the

spectra to be prepared for PCA transformation, thus reducing the information volume the machine learning algorithm should process. For the sample classification, a hierarchical PLS-DA model was trained to discriminate the plastic samples in multiple phases, with the last one being a binary classification problem of predicting if the sample belongs to either the HDPE or LDPE class. It is worth mentioning that only the samples whose class has not been identified in previous steps would reach the last phase of the model's hierarchical scheme. The proposed pipeline, during its testing phase, had sensitivity and specificity **> 91%** in all classes.

In the wood by-products characterization domain, there is no extended literature, especially when the optical sensor is an RGB camera. Htun et al. (2021), proposed a transfer learning methodology for the classification of wood samples into heartwood and sapwood respectively. Their methodology is based on the Cifar10Net, previously trained on the RGB CIFAR10 dataset. In order to feed the network with hyperspectral images of 320 channels, the authors had to modify the input layer of the network to accept images of such shape. Moreover, a custom algorithm was implemented in order to solve the aforementioned binary problem without having to completely replace the top layer of the used network which has 10 neurons. The proposed architecture was, subsequently, trained in 3 phases. In the first phase, only the output layer was trained keeping the rest of the weights frozen, in the second phase the input layer was trained in the same manner, and lastly, a fine-tuning of the network's weights was performed during the third phase of the training. The proposed model achieved around **94%** accuracy during testing.

The objectives of our work include the introduction of a new deep learning methodology capable of exploiting spatial and spectral information from multiple optical modalities, in order to improve the plastic waste segregation and the wood by-products up-cycling processes. In this manner, a *multi-encoder* architecture is proposed and tested on a custom dataset, created for the needs of this work, that consists of three different modalities for each object, viz. (i) RGB, (ii) VIS and (iii) NIR images.

3. Methodology

A detailed description of the proposed vision-based agnostic system for separating plastic and wood waste streams is provided. The proposed system identifies the position of the object/waste within the conveyor, synchronizes the different cameras (RGB and multi-spectral) and utilizes the gathered information from all cameras in order to classify the type of object. The goal of this process is to identify the location, the trajectory and the type of the object(s). This information usually is transmitted to the corresponding automated picking process, i.e. the robotic arm.

As shown in Fig. 3, our architecture is composed of three modules, communicating with each other: (i) the *detection module*, an Artificial

Fig. 3. This figure shows the high-level flowchart of the information exchange among the system modules.

Intelligence (AI) model responsible for the initial detection and segmentation of the object on the conveyor; (ii) the synchronization module, being used to ensure all of the system's modules refer to the same object and (iii) the *multi-modal classification* module, that is an auto-encoder like AI model responsible to leverage the information from all different modalities, aiming to classify accurately the type of the object under investigation.

3.1. Detection module

This module is an AI-driven model responsible to identify an object's presence along the conveyor belt and to derive certain initial conditions e.g. the timestamp it passes through the centre of the RGB frame, as well as its centroid, shape and perimeter.

As an object conveys along the belt, the industrial RGB camera is the first sensing device that interacts with it, capturing videos at a 30 fps rate. Each RGB frame is fed to the *detection module*, which is responsible for the object localisation within each frame's boundaries. In detail, a deep neural network trained for segmentation tasks is utilized for that process. Within this process, the frames are analysed in real-time and a binary mask of each object that appears in the frame is created. A unique digital ID is, also, assigned to every binary mask, thus preventing double detection of the same object. The segmented frames undergo further post-processing, in order to identify the video frame which depicts the object(s) as centred as possible with respect to the frame's boundaries, and subsequently saves those frames, and their respective masks to a database for potential future use. Finally, the timestamp, indicating the mask creation instance, and the mask's coordinates on the conveyor are fed to the synchronization module.

3.2. Synchronisation module

The synchronization module is responsible for the orchestration of all the components of the cyber-physical system. It receives the initial position, the timestamp t_0 and the ID of each object from the *detection module*. Additionally, the synchronization module is aware of the sorter mechanical parameters, i.e. conveyor speed, the position of each camera and the position of the robotic arm.

The goal of the synchronization module is twofold: (i) It calculates the proper time and triggers each component to take an action, e.g. inform the NIR camera that the object is at the centre of its field of view at time $t_{trigger}$ or the robotic arm about the proper picking time t_{pick} for a given object, and (ii) it keeps all the necessary metadata necessary for the dataset generation for the re-training of the AI algorithms, i.e. the captures from the different cameras that depict the same object (Fig. 4).

After $t_{trigger}$ time, a trigger is sent to the multi-spectral cameras. Due to the fact that the lenses of the two multi-spectral cameras are not aligned, this module is also responsible for selecting the correct spectral frame pixels.

3.3. Classification module

The last module comprises the computer vision classifier subsystem of the proposed architecture the *Classification Module*. This module is

Fig. 4. This figure presents the stages of the proposed agnostic vision-based module, which identifies the perimeter, and the centre of the object while synchronising the cameras to capture data for the prediction model.

responsible for leveraging the information from all different modalities (i.e. RGB, VIS and NIR images), and identifying the class/type of the object of interest. In order to extract information from the different data sources, this module relies on an auto-encoder-based architecture. In particular, multiple parallel encoders are utilized, one for each modality. The encoders' output is, subsequently, decoded to extract the class of each object. The classification output is transferred to the robotic subsystem to guide the waste collection and separation. In the following section, an in-depth presentation of the machine learning algorithms implemented for this work is provided.

4. Implementation

In this chapter, the technical details of the proposed modules in Chapter 3 are discussed, along with the deep architectures for each of the selected algorithms. For better understanding and reproducibility purposes, an in-depth analysis of the training and re-training processes of each model is presented, along with the loss functions utilized in this work and the training hyper-parameters. Finally, the optimization process of the various parameters, e.g. segmentation model weights, multi-modal parameters etc, is explained in a systematic manner, providing insights into the learning process undergoing in the proposed system.

A set up comprising three cameras has been utilized, each of them capturing different regions of the electromagnetic spectrum. In detail, the vision-sensing devices are as follows:

- Industrial RGB camera: 400 - 700 nm (3 bands)
- Visible Spectrum (VIS) multi-spectral camera: 480 - 620 nm (16 bands)
- Near-Infrared Spectrum (NIR) multi-spectral camera: 720 - 970 nm (25 bands)

In detail, the *Industrial RGB* camera acquires three-channel (red, green, blue) images at 60 fps framerate. For the materials' analysis and differentiation based on their distinct spectral signatures, a set of multi-spectral cameras, that acquire multi-band images, was utilized. The so-called *spectral bands* are specific wavelengths or ranges of wavelengths that encode information about a material's reflectance or absorbance properties Nasrabadi (2014). The *VIS multi-spectral* camera is capable of sampling the visible range of the spectrum (480 - 620 nm), capturing information of 16 distinct spectral bands with an average step of 9 nm. Moreover, the *NIR multi-spectral* camera samples 25 distinct spectral bands in the Near-Infrared range (720 - 970 nm) of the spectrum

Table 1

The distinct spectral bands captured by each multi-spectral modality.

Multi-spectral Modality	Sampled Bands (nm)
VIS	477, 478, 490, 500, 511, 523, 538, 549, 553, 563, 577, 591, 600, 613, 616, 618
NIR	713, 714, 737, 750, 763, 776, 788, 801, 813, 825, 842, 854, 865, 875, 885, 895, 904, 913, 926, 934, 944, 949, 961, 966, 971

with an average sampling step of 10 nm. Table 1 provides, in detail, the wavelengths captured by each of the multi-spectral modalities.

The selection of the aforementioned wavelengths for multi-spectral analysis of the waste stream is underpinned by two fundamental considerations. Firstly, the chosen wavelengths necessitate short integration times for the acquisition of comprehensive spectral information. Secondly, the wavelengths in question are intricately associated with cost-effective laboratory equipment. The availability of affordable optical detectors, and filters tailored to these wavelengths streamlines the procurement and maintenance of experimental apparatus, thereby minimizing resource expenditure. Consequently, this wavelength selection strategy aligns with the dual objectives of optimizing data acquisition and analysis efficiency, ensuring real-time operation, while retaining operational costs as low as possible.

In this manner, each object in the dataset MMWD consists of $X = \{X_{rgb}, X_{vir}, X_{vis}\}$, where the components represent the information captured by the corresponding camera. Additionally, each object is characterised by its labelling information Y .

In our case $Y = \{Y_{cls}, Y_{seg}\}$, where Y_{cls} represents the class of the object, while Y_{seg} denotes its binary mask in RGB images. The Y_{cls} consists of 7 in totally different classes, 4 different types of plastic and 3 different types of wood, as can be seen in Table 2.

4.1. MMWD dataset

The sorter's multi-spectral cameras are equipped with snapshot mosaic sensors capturing an object's spectral information, in an interleaved manner, resulting in a greyscale image of shape 2016×1080 pixels. Reverse decoupling method was implemented in order to acquire the so-called 3D hypercubes with 512×272 spatial resolution. Prior to this, the grabbed images were scanned for corrupted pixels (i.e. pixels with NaN, zero, or infinite values) and upon identification, these pixels were substituted by the median value of their 2×2 neighbourhood. The resulting hypercubes are, in fact, 3D tensors that combine spatial information in their first two dimensions with an object's spectral properties in the third dimension.

The digital data acquired by the multi-spectral cameras in their raw form are representative of radiance values, contingent upon the specific configuration employed during the acquisition process. Notably, the quantum efficiency (QE) of the sensor (comprising both the sensor proper and the accompanying interference filter) exhibits wavelength-dependent variability. To counterbalance the influence stemming from the comprehensive setup parameters (encompassing QE characteristics, optical path transmission coefficients, and the spatial as well as spectral fluctuations in the illumination field), a linear transformation is engaged to ascertain the so-called reflectance values, that inherently encapsulate the nuanced absorption or reflectance properties of materials. To this end, white and black reference images were captured to model the true maximum value the cameras detect and the static noise apparent in the two multi-spectral snapshot mosaic sensors respectively. It is worth mentioning that for the acquisition of the white reference image, a calibration white surface with uniform reflective properties was utilised along entire examined wavelengths, while the conversion process is explained by Equation (1):

Fig. 5. The laboratory CPSS, where the dataset was created using the RGB and multi-spectral cameras Konstantinidis et al. (2023b); Balakera et al. (2023).

Fig. 6. The four types of plastics (HDPE, LDPE, PET and PP) and three types of woods (MDF, MFC and Oak Veneer) of the MMWD dataset are presented.

$$R = \frac{O - D^O}{W - D^{Ref}} \frac{t_{Ref}}{t_O}, \quad (1)$$

where R is the reflectance image, O is the original image captured by each camera sensor, W is the white reference image captured with the help of the calibration surface, D^{Ref} is the black reference image captured with integration time equal to the integration time used for the capturing of the white reference image, D^O reflects the black reference image captured with integration time equal to the integration time used for capturing the object's image, t_{Ref} is the integration time used for capturing the white reference image, and t_O is the integration time used for capturing the object's image. Due to different brightness levels of the object and the reflectance target, the respective integration times may be different, hence the corrected images are multiplied by the ratio $\frac{t_{Ref}}{t_O}$ to normalize the pixel values in the range of $[0 - 1]$.

In particular, the MMWD dataset includes images from plastic and wood by-product samples of various shapes and sizes, while the CPSS, from which the photographs were obtained, is illustrated in Fig. 5. Specifically, plastic waste consists of PP, PET, LDPE, and HDPE, while wood waste consists of MDF, MFC, and Oak Veneer, as shown in Fig. 6.

In total, 684 distinct objects were selected, placed on the CPSS' belt and 1086 images were grabbed (by each sensor) and the distribution among the different materials is presented in Table 2. The dataset images are further augmented by rotation, translation and pixel-value transformation, to end up with a dataset size 30 times as large as the initial one. This step was mandatory, in order to result in a sufficient amount of images for training the *multi-encoder classifier*.

4.2. Detection module

In the last years, remarkable progress has been made in the domain of computer vision with the advent of advanced object detection and

Table 2
Distribution among the seven materials of the *MMWD*.

Category	Plastic				Wood		
Type	HDPE	LDPE	PET	PP	MDF	MFC	Oak
Number	103	102	290	263	94	114	120

segmentation models Konstantinidis et al. (2023a); Burgos Simon et al. (2023). Various state-of-the-art neural network architectures have been proposed in an attempt to address the problems mentioned above, namely YOLO-v8 Jocher et al. (2023), Mask R-CNN He et al. (2017), RetinaNet Lin et al. (2017). In terms of this work, the emphasis lies on achieving a balance between real-time video processing and maintaining the accuracy and precision of the aforementioned segmentation models, thus the YOLO-v8 architecture is utilised to localize the objects moving along the conveyor belt. The rationale behind this decision is that this architecture is capable of segmenting the objects apparently in an image by analysing it in a single step, as opposed to the Mask R-CNN approach, hence achieving real-time object detection. Moreover, the precision of the binary masks generated by the YOLO-v8 model is comparable to the one achieved by Mask R-CNN, thus rendering this architecture a suitable candidate for the proposed architecture.

YOLO-v8 is designed to scan the entire image at different scales and identify objects of various sizes that are depicted. To this end, a multi-scale feature extraction, pyramid-shaped architecture, based on Darknet-53, has been adopted as the backbone of the network, which divides an image into a collection of smaller regions to extract visual features and encode them in activation maps Ahmed et al. (2023). These activation maps are subsequently fed to the multi-head part of the network, which is responsible for estimating a bounding box and the respective class probabilities for the objects present in the input image.

Model re-training

The initial model is pre-trained on the COCO dataset, which contains 91 classes of common objects with a total of 2.5 million labelled instances distributed in 328k images Lin et al. (2014). To adapt the model to the needs of this work, i.e. to detect plastic and wood waste moving along the conveyor belt and to generate the respective binary mask, the model should be retrained. This adaptation is achieved by re-training the model using the RGB images X_{rgb} and their corresponding masked version Y_{seg} .

For model re-training, images of size $640 \times 640 \times 3$ were used and augmentation techniques were applied, including *scale*, *translation*, *flips*, *rotation*, *pixel-value exposure* and *brightness*, *noise addition*, *colour sift*, and *mosaic collection*. Additionally, the cost function is:

$$CostFunction = CE(\hat{Y}_{label}, Y_{label}) + DFL(\hat{Y}_{seg}, Y_{seg}) + SL(\hat{Y}_{seg}, Y_{seg}), \quad (2)$$

where,

$$CE(X, Y) = - \sum_{c=1}^C \log \frac{\exp(x_c)}{\sum_{i=1}^C \exp(x_i)} y_c, \quad (3)$$

$$DFL(X, Y) = -((y_{i+1} - y) \log(x_i) + (y - y_i) \log(x_{i+1})), \quad (4)$$

$$SL(X, Y) = 1 - IoU(X, Y) + \frac{d^2}{l^2}, \quad (5)$$

CE is the cross entropy loss that indicates the classification performance for C classes, DFL depicts the distribution focal loss, which captures the deviation of the predicted and the actual mask shape and SL represents the IoU-based segmentation loss function that quantifies the non-intersected area of the predicted and the ground truth segmentation mask. The constants d is the distance between the center pixels of the bounding boxes and l the maximum distance between the outermost pixels of the two respective bounding boxes. The cost function is minimized with the stochastic gradient descent algorithm Ruder (2016). As shown in Fig. 8, through the re-training of the model, the components

Fig. 7. The architecture of the proposed *multi-encoder classifier*.

of the cost function are decreasing monotonically in the training set, in contrast with the validation set where convergence is slower with some fluctuations in the validation set. This behaviour of the loss functions, during the re-training, is indicative of the segmentation model's ability to fit on the dataset and create precise masks of the objects. During the validation procedure, the three loss functions exhibit a decreasing trend overall, despite some fluctuations. This trend demonstrates the model's ability to generalize its inference beyond the training samples and perform well on new data.

4.3. Classification module

The goal of the classification module is to allocate the correct label to each of the unknown objects on the conveyor. In order to achieve that, the multi-modal classification model collects the information of the object of interest from the three cameras (X_{rgb} , X_{vis} , X_{nir}), processes them in the auto-encoder and finally predicts the label of the object. As shown in Fig. 7, the multi-modal classification architecture contains multiple parallel encoders. The information of each different modality passes through a separate encoder. The output of the encoders is merged in a common latent space and finally, the object's latent space representation is forwarded to the decoder.

The goal of the proposed design is to take advantage of the information contained in each of the modalities (RGB, VIS or NIR images) to capture the inherent correlations and dependencies among multiple modalities, i.e. spatio-spectral correlations. Multi-modal fusion offers a more sophisticated approach by integrating information across modalities, enabling the extraction of more complex features and enhancing overall predictive performance.

Model training

As shown in Fig. 7, the system comprising three encoders, one for each information modal (X_{rgb} , X_{vis} , X_{nir}). For simplicity and clarity, each of the encoders follows the same architecture of ResNet-18. ResNet-18 is a CNN architecture, designed specifically for image classification tasks and has achieved state-of-the-art performance on various benchmark data sets He et al. (2015).

The model's training took place in two steps, the encoders' initialization and the overall training of the model. Initially, training is conducted separately for each encoder, corresponding to each information modality. Subsequently, the representations learned by each encoder are merged into a common representation, and the entire system is trained simultaneously. This two-step process enhances the robustness of the system by reducing the risk of getting trapped at a local minimum that is far from the global optimum solution.

Let $M = \{RGB, VIS, NIR\}$ be the set of all the different modalities. For each $m \in M$, we define $E_m(\cdot | \theta_m)$ the encoder of each modality and

its corresponding tunable parameters θ_m . In the initialization phase, an extra soft-max layer is added after the encoder and we find the optimal θ_m^* by minimizing the cross-entropy loss (CE)

$$\min_{\theta_m} CE(E_m(X_m|\theta_m), Y) . \quad (6)$$

In detail, post appending the soft-max layer to each $E_m(\cdot|\theta_m)$ encoder, for $m \in M$, the three models were independently trained. Let $S(E_m(X_m|\theta_m)) := q_m(X_m)$ be the output of the m^{th} encoder after the soft-max. Each $q_m(\cdot)$ model was fit to classify the X_m instances to their respective classes. Following Equation (6), upon minimization of the $CE(q_m(X_m), Y)$ the optimal θ_m are calculated and thus the encoder initialization phase is terminated.

For the minimization, the adaptive stochastic gradient descent algorithm was utilized Kingma and Ba Adam (2017). For simplicity, let $E_m(X_m|\theta_m) := z_m(X_m)$ denote the representation of objects X of m^{th} encoder, before the soft-max layer. The representations of each modality are merged into a single representation per object

$$z = z_{RGB} + z_{VIS} + z_{NIR} . \quad (7)$$

The representations z are the input of the decoder layer as shown in Fig. 7. Let θ_{dec} be the tunable parameters of the decoder and $\theta = \{\theta_{RGB}, \theta_{VIS}, \theta_{NIR}, \theta_{dec}\}$ the overall set of the parameters of the model. The modalities of each object and its label Y are used to calculate the optimal parameters θ^* by minimizing the cross entropy

$$\min_{\theta} CE(D(z|\theta), Y) , \quad (8)$$

where $D(z|\theta_{dec})$ represents the decoder's output, which after passing through the final softmax layer transforms into the network's final prediction, i.e. $D(z|\theta)$.

Optimisation is achieved with the use of adaptive stochastic gradient descent. Once the overall training of the multi-encoder architecture is completed, the system can effectively leverage the information from each camera and estimate the object's class. Mathematically, this can be expressed by combining the aforementioned information with the following equation:

$$D(z_{RGB}(X_{rgb}) + z_{VIS}(X_{vis}) + z_{NIR}(X_{nir}) | \theta) = \hat{Y} , \quad (9)$$

5. Results

For the performance evaluation of the *segmentation model* and *multi-encoder classifier* the test subset was used, which contains 20% of the original images as described in subsection 4.1. Although no cross-validation scheme was followed due to the adopted rule during the creation of the train and test subsets, a strong guarantee of the effectiveness of the evaluation methodology is provided by ensuring that the same physical object does not appear in both datasets.

5.1. Detection performance

As far as the *detection module* is concerned, the training process was concluded after 200 epochs, although the best performance based on the validation set, which was created by extracting 10% from the train set, was achieved in epoch 175. During this epoch, the model's mean average precision (mAP50) for the mask was equal to **0.99** on the training set and **0.97** on the validation set. In Fig. 8, the progression of the metrics used for the model's evaluation is depicted. In detail, examining the loss curves, both for the training and the validation set, it is observed that a slow but continuous decrease in their value exists, indicating a successful fitting of the model to the dataset's distribution. Moreover, a steep value reduction is noticed around epoch 175 in the curves regarding the training set, proving once again that this was the epoch in the model that exhibited the best performance. Finally, inspection of the precision and mAP50 curves regarding the model's masking

efficiency, shows that these curves flatten in much earlier epochs than the respective curves. Around epoch 100 the model was able to achieve **>95%** precision and **>98%** mAP50, meaning that the algorithm is both accurate in terms of detection while the segmented masks are almost identical to the actual perimeter of the objects.

In Fig. 9, an example of the segmentation results is shown, accompanied by the respective bounding boxes and predicted class. In the examples below, the model's high segmentation performance can, once again, be verified, as the generated masks are of high precision, with well-defined contours and minimum inclusion of background pixels to each object's mask.

5.2. Classification performance

RGB Classifier: In order to validate the classification performance of the proposed system, initially an RGB classifier was trained with the 80% of the original dataset and tested with the remaining 20%. The ResNet-18 classifier architecture was selected. The overall accuracy of the classifier in the test set was 91%. Fig. 10 presents the confusion matrix of the RGB baseline classifier, which showcases the model's ability to classify objects at a high level. Specifically, it demonstrates the model's capability to accurately distinguish wood by-products from plastic waste. However, the performance drops in the more complex task of identifying the subcategory of each sample $x \in X_{rgb}$. In detail, a few (4.8%) *MDF* samples are falsely classified as *MFC*, while 14% of them are identified as *Oak Veneer*. For the rest of the wood by-products, 4.3% of *MFC* samples are classified as *MDF*, while 4.5% of the images depicting *Oak Veneer* samples are classified as *MFC*. Although the aforementioned misclassification percentages per class might seem insignificant, they translate to a 9.1% classification error for the wood by-products.

For the plastic waste case, the model's performance is almost identical to the wood by-products classification case, with a classification error equal to 9.2%. In detail, *LDPE* is the class the model struggles the most to discriminate from the rest, with almost 30% of the samples being classified either as *PET* or *PP*. Moreover, the *RGB Classifier* confuses a small percentage of *PET* samples with *PP* and vice versa. An exception to the aforementioned points is the case of *HDPE* samples, where the model's precision and recall for the type of plastic waste are **100%**. Overall, the model achieves recall **> 91%** in most of the classes, with *MDF* and *LDPE* being the ones that the model struggles the most to identify.

Multi-modal classifier: The evaluation of the *multi-encoder classifier* was conducted under a scheme similar to RGB classifier. In detail, the same test set was used, but this time the three X_{rgb}^{test} , X_{vis}^{test} , X_{nir}^{test} subsets were utilised.

After the final 100 epochs of training, the proposed model was able to achieve **99%** accuracy on the train set and **96%** on the validation set. Fig. 11 shows the progression of the loss function and the accuracy score of the *multi-encoder classifier* during the training phase. Upon examining the loss curves, it becomes apparent that the model effectively adapts to the working dataset without exhibiting any indications of overfitting. This is evident from the smooth decrease in both the train and validation losses as epochs progress. Moreover, the minor spikes apparent in the validation loss curve should not be considered a sign of the model overfitting the training dataset; on the contrary, they are proof that the samples in the training and validation set are not identical and since they tend to reduce in amplitude over time, it should be considered as an indication of the model's generalization ability.

In Fig. 12, the classification results of the proposed *multi-encoder* model are presented in the form of a confusion matrix. The values mentioned in the cells of the aforementioned matrix are normalized once again with respect to the number of instances in each class. By inspecting the graph, it is evident that the model demonstrates a strong ability to fit the data in the train set while maintaining high generalization

Fig. 8. Evolution of loss functions and metrics utilized during *detection module* training and validation.

Fig. 9. Examples of the segmentation output for each class by the *detection module*.

Fig. 10. Confusion matrix describing baseline model efficiency in predicting the right class of the object detected in each frame.

properties. This is reflected in its capacity to correctly classify a majority of the samples present in the test set. In detail, the proposed architecture, after training, was able to discriminate all the samples of *MFC*, *HDPE* and *LDPE* samples from the rest of the instances, thus achieving **100%** recall in those classes. A small percentage (4.5%) of the *Oak Veneer* samples were falsely assigned to the *MDF* class, while some confusion is identified when discriminating the *PET* samples from

Fig. 11. Evolution of the cross-entropy loss and overall accuracy of the multi-encoder classifier, both on the train and the validation set, during the second phase of its training.

the *PP* samples and vice versa. Furthermore, a small percentage (2%) of *LDPE* samples are misclassified as *PP*. In general, the *multi-modal classifier* achieved more than **95%** recall in all classes, except for the case of *MDF* that multiple samples were misclassified as *Oak Veneer*, and **96%** total accuracy. It is worth mentioning that any errors made by the proposed architecture were limited to the same general category, namely wood and plastic. This translates to a **100%** accuracy in distinguishing wood by-products from plastic waste.

Table 3 presents a compact comparison between our *emphmulti-modal classifier* and the corresponding single-source classifiers. The metrics used for the evaluation of the models, i.e. *precision*, *recall*, *f1-score* and *accuracy*, are presented. Based on those metrics, it can easily be verified that the proposed architecture has superior performance in terms of accuracy, as the best single-source classifier, i.e. the *RGB classifier*, achieves **91%** accuracy, **5%** less than the *multi-encoder classifier's*. Moreover, the proposed model is capable of increasing the worst F1 score of the single source in each class.

Table 3
Evaluation metrics for RGB, VIS, NIR and proposed classifiers on the same test set.

	RGB			VIS			NIR			Multi-Encoder			
	precision	recall	f1-score	precision	recall	f1-score	precision	recall	f1-score	precision	recall	f1-score	support
HDPE	1.00	1.00	1.00	0.64	0.73	0.68	0.94	0.73	0.82	1.00	1.00	1.00	21
LDPE	1.00	0.68	0.81	1.00	0.77	0.87	0.77	0.91	0.83	0.96	1.00	0.98	23
MDF	0.94	0.81	0.87	0.90	0.86	0.88	1.00	0.95	0.98	0.95	0.86	0.90	22
MFC	0.92	0.96	0.94	1.00	1.00	1.00	0.92	1.00	0.96	1.00	1.00	1.00	22
OAK-VENEER	0.88	0.95	0.91	0.87	0.91	0.89	0.95	0.91	0.93	0.88	0.95	0.91	22
PET	0.88	0.91	0.90	0.86	0.89	0.88	0.84	0.81	0.82	0.98	0.96	0.97	57
PP	0.88	0.96	0.92	0.82	0.82	0.82	0.78	0.82	0.80	0.96	0.96	0.96	51
Accuracy	0.91			0.86			0.86			0.96			

Fig. 12. Confusion Matrix of the *multi-encoder classifier*, presenting the percentage of correctly classified instances out of each class.

5.3. Asset performance

The training and evaluation of the AI models, employed in this work, were executed on an experimental computational setup. The hardware configuration comprised of a 16-core central processing unit (CPU), 20 GB of DDR4 RAM and a NVIDIA RTX A4000 GPU with 48 GB of VRAM. The inference time for detection model was, on average, 9 ms, while the multi-modal classification model required 19 ms to analyse a frame. In total, the localization and characterization of each object apparent in a video frame took 28 ms, which proves the proposed system’s capacity to sort waste streams in real-time. Finally, the robotic sub-system, controlled by the same setup, is ample to perform up to 45 picks/minute which defines the overall sorting performance of the system.

5.4. Limitations: a closer look at the misclassified objects

For the case of the *PP* sample categorized as *PET*, it should be mentioned that the sample is dark-coloured (dark green) which results in a low-quality spectrum signal since most of the energy of the lighting source is absorbed on the material’s surface. Furthermore, the *PP* sample assigned to *LDPE* seems to have a different texture from most of the *PP* samples, looking more like an *LDPE* object, hence making the model assign the sample to that class. The surface of the misclassified *PET* sample is, mainly, covered by a tag, which is highly possible to be either a different kind of plastic or a mixture of plastics, thus producing false data. Finally, regarding the *Oak Veneer* sample that was categorized as *MDF*, one can notice that both its shape and texture are similar to the *MDF* ones. Also, the area of this object is not big enough to ex-

Fig. 13. Mis-classified objects by the proposed *multi-encoder classifier*. The model’s prediction is shown on top of each image, while inside the parenthesis is indicated the true class of each object.

tract adequate spectral information to assist in the correct classification of the sample. The RGB images of the misclassified objects mentioned above are shown in Fig. 13.

5.5. Latent space visualisation

In order to better understand the classification results and visualize the output of each classifier, the TSNE algorithm was utilized to project the multidimensional outputs of each model in a 2D space. In Fig. 14, the projected output space of each single-source classifier is presented on the left side prior to training and on the right side after training for the same number of epochs using the same dataset.

In the aforementioned figure, the evolution of each single-source classifier output space is depicted. In detail, the samples in all three spaces, before training, appear to be randomly distributed in the 2D projection plane. After training, the RGB classifier appears to have adequately fitted the training data set, where distinct clusters have formed. It is also worth mentioning that the types of objects, i.e. wood and plastic waste, are clearly separated from each other since they populate different regions of the 2D plane. In the case of the NIR classifier, some clusters can also be identified with much higher distribution over the plane, hence indicating the model’s lesser accuracy in discriminating the various classes. Specifically, the output space of the VIS classifier proves the model’s struggle to identify the different types of wood by-products, as well as discriminate them from PP samples. Finally, in the output space of the NIR classifier, apart from the *HDPE*, *LDPE* and *PET* cases, it is difficult to identify any clear clusters, which is why the relatively low performance of this model is so low.

The single-source classifiers, although capable of identifying to a certain level the different classes of the objects in the test dataset, they lack total prediction accuracy. In this manner, the combination of the aforementioned classifiers in the form of the proposed *Multi-Encoder* architecture offers a more efficient utilization of the information acquired

Fig. 14. In the upper half of this figure the latent space of the fully-trained single-source classifiers is depicted, while on the lower half of the figure, the evolution of the latent space of the proposed multi-modal classifier is presented. On the left side the initial latent space (with no training) is depicted, the middle subfigure presents the same space after 10 epochs of training, while on the lower right side the final latent space -post training- is shown.

from the different modalities, thus providing better classification results with fewer samples being misclassified.

The output space of the proposed model, when no further training has taken place, appears to have the samples less randomly distributed in space. This fact can easily be explained, considering that knowledge from the aforementioned classifiers has been transferred to the proposed one since they are being used as pre-trained encoders. However, the decoder layer of the *multi-encoder classifier* has undergone no training up to this point, hence the lack of distinct clusters. The distribution of the samples in the 2D projection space changes drastically once the fine-tuning of the proposed model is completed. In detail, plastic waste samples clearly occupy the leftmost and rightmost regions of the 2D space, whereas the wood by-product samples are distributed along the y-axis, almost in the middle of the x-axis, proving once again the model's ability to discriminate plastic waste from wood by-products with **100%** accuracy. Furthermore, clear clusters have formed for each of the seven classes, with only a few samples being assigned to the wrong class cluster.

In conclusion, the proposed architecture proves to be a robust and accurate solution for classifying various types of common plastic waste and wood by-products. Its innovative approach enables the simultaneous processing of data from multiple modalities through a single neural network, thereby enhancing the overall accuracy of predictions.

6. Conclusion and future work

In this paper, a new approach accentuating on a *multi-modal classifier* is proposed. Our method is capable of categorising waste, while it also employs a detector to identify objects on conveyor belts. The proposed technique aims to enhance robotic waste sorting applications by addressing the inherent challenges posed by clutter and the diverse range of waste materials. Unlike conventional machine vision methods that struggle to cope with such complexities, our approach acknowledges the need for alternative sensors. By incorporating these sensors into the sorting process, we manage to overcome the limitations and

improve the efficiency and accuracy of waste sorting in a more practical and effective manner.

To this end, a synchronisation module coordinates the RGB, and multi-spectral sensors to timely capture images. Multiple parallel auto-encoders are used to extract spatio-spectral information from RGB, VIS and NIR sensors and project them in a common latent space, to finally decode them and predict the class of each object. By validating our novel approach in a custom dataset, viz. MMWD, which was also presented here for the first time and contains plastic (HDPE, LDPE, PET, PP) and wood (MDF, MFC, Oak veneer) wastes, it is shown that the system performs with accuracy and precision. More specifically, Yolo v8 was trained to successfully segment the waste within the conveyor, achieving the segmentation map 99.5%. During the evaluation phase of the models, where the single-source classifiers for RGB, VIS, and NIR achieved an accuracy of **91%**, **86%**, and **86%** respectively, the novel *multi-encoder classifier* achieved **96%** accuracy by using spectral and spatial modalities. In this manner, the proposed *Multi-Encoder* architecture enhances the utilisation of information obtained from various modalities, leading to improved classification results with a reduced number of misclassified samples.

The proposed architecture, however, despite its novelty and high classification performance, exhibits certain limitations. Specifically, dark-coloured or black objects are misclassified, as most of the visible and near-infrared light is absorbed on their surface, resulting in minimal reflected radiation to be captured by the system's optical sensors and analysed by the AI models. Moreover, multi-spectral imaging spectroscopy is a very powerful tool for capturing and analysing the spectral properties of a material's surface. In this manner, however, the proposed system is proven insufficient to segregate waste streams that contain multi-layer objects, since such samples are sorted based only on their outer layer. Consequently, the aforementioned limitations, except for an incentive for future work, they could serve as common guidelines for packaging design, so that the produced amount of such objects could be reduced, thus upgrading the valorisation of waste streams.

In our forthcoming research, we intend to investigate hyperspectral sensors that encompass a wavelength range of up to 5000 nm. Our

objective is to enhance the spatial information contained within each pixel. Additionally, we expect to examine the impact of lighting conditions on the sensor's performance. Finally, we will explore how the addition of new modalities (e.g. X-ray) affects the overall performance of the system.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Fotios K. Konstantinidis: Conceptualization, Data curation, Formal analysis, Funding acquisition, Investigation, Methodology, Project administration, Supervision, Validation, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing. **Savvas Sifnaios:** Conceptualization, Data curation, Investigation, Methodology, Project administration, Software, Visualization, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing. **George Arvanitakis:** Data curation, Investigation, Methodology, Project administration, Software, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing. **Georgios Tsimiklis:** Conceptualization, Funding acquisition, Investigation, Methodology, Resources, Validation, Writing – review & editing. **Spyridon G. Mouroutsos:** Formal analysis, Methodology, Visualization, Writing – review & editing. **Angelos Amditis:** Formal analysis, Funding acquisition, Resources, Supervision, Writing – review & editing. **Antonios Gasteratos:** Conceptualization, Formal analysis, Project administration, Resources, Supervision, Validation, Writing – review & editing.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare the following financial interests/personal relationships which may be considered as potential competing interests: Fotios K. Konstantinidis reports financial support was provided by Institute of Communication and Computer Systems.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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